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Comparison of marginal adaptation of fiber reinforced composite and metal ceramic full veneer crown

T Hassan¹, S Ferdous², AM Aurangjeb³

Abstract

Fiber reinforcement was introduced to clinical dentistry for the first time in the 1960s when investigators attempted to reinforce polymethyl-methacrylate dentures with glass or carbon fibers. It has recently been shown that crowns, bridges and posts made of FRC can be used successfully in dental practice and on the basis of marginal adaptation they are more acceptable than conventional metal ceramic crown. A prospective comparative cross-sectional study was performed involving 60 patients who attended in the out patients department of Prosthodontics, Faculty of Dentistry, BSMMU during the period of January 2007 to December 2008. Clinical data were recorded for the selected 60 patients who were divided into two groups "experimental" and "control". Marginal adaptation was indexed after California Dental Associations quality evaluation system. The age of the patients ranged from 18 to 42 years in group A and 17 to 38 years in group B. The highest number of patients was in the age group 21-30 years in both the groups. The mean age was 24.9±5.8 years and 25.0±4.8 years in group A and group B respectively. There were 26 male and 34 female patients in the study and male female ratio was 1:1.3. In group A patients, 12(40.0%) were male and 18(60.0%) female. In group B patients 14(46.7%) were male and 16(53.3%) were female. After 4 months all the patients were in grade I in both the groups. After 8 months all the patients were in grade I in group A and 27(90.0%) patients in grade I in group B. After 12 months all the patients were in grade I in group A and 25(83.3%) patients were in grade I in group B. The difference was not statistically significant ($p>0.05$) after 8 months, however after 12 months the difference was significant ($p<0.05$). The Fiber Reinforced Composite crown represents a valuable development in the field of Prosthetic Dentistry.

Key words: Marginal adaptation, Fiber reinforced Composite crown, Metal ceramic crown.

Introduction

Metal-ceramic crowns are clinically successful¹. But the visibility of metal and the change in natural tooth translucency is aesthetically unfavorable. The desire for natural looking restorations has encouraged research in the last decades on metal-free, tooth colored materials for dental restorations.²

In early all-ceramic restorations exhibited high failure rates,³ an alternative has been found in the use of reinforced composite materials. In recent years, there have been several in vitro⁴⁻⁶ and in vivo studies^{7,8} of the properties of these composites and promising results have been reported for crowns,⁹ and for fixed partial dentures.¹⁰

However, although these materials seem to provide excellent aesthetics,¹¹ some authors do not recommend composite materials for permanent restorations,^{12,13} because of their unstable aesthetics, their increased wear¹⁴ and their liability to plaque accumulation.¹⁵

With the introduction of fiber reinforced composites, it seemed to be possible to eliminate these disadvantages of composites and to exploit their advantages, including the simple laboratory procedure, the lower costs and the possibility of repair.

Additionally, this new generation of composites has given promising in vitro results with respect to color change,¹⁶ wear¹⁷ and fracture resistance.¹⁸

The objective of this present prospective clinical study was to assess marginal adaptation of a new experimental fiber reinforced composite anterior crowns, compared with a metal-ceramic control group.

Methods

Participants for this study were recruited from patients visiting the Department of Prosthodontics Faculty of Dentistry, BSMMU during the period of January 2007 to December 2008. The university's review board approved the study and all patients signed an informed consent form. Criteria for including was-Fracture teeth with healthy periodontal tissue,

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discolored anterior teeth, endodontically treated tooth (Root canal treated tooth), abrasion, erosion of anterior teeth and excluding premolar and molar teeth, periodontally compromised teeth, para functional habit (bruxer), vertical fracture, grossly damaged teeth, developmentally defective teeth; all evaluated by the researcher.

Clinical treatment – at chair side and in laboratory site a standardized procedure was followed. After the removal of old restorative materials and caries excavation, the teeth were built up according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Adaptation of Fiber: Pre impregnated resin, flat & unidirectional Dentapreg fiber strip manufactured by Prestige Dental, UK was used for fabrication of framework of crown. Bucco-lingual length of the restoration was measured by scale & Dentapreg fiber strip was cut down according to measurement.

Covering paper of Dentapreg strip was removed and adapted one side of the fiber –reinforced composite (FRC) on the buccal side teeth and visible light (Litex) was applied for 20 seconds. Then the fiber –reinforced composite was shaped and adapted slowly lingual side teeth and light curing was applied for 20 seconds. Then the transparent plastic protective film on the strip was removed.

Composite build up: By the incremental way the hybrid veneering composite (ceramic nano-Densply) was applied over the abutments/die and light curing was applied for 40 seconds. The medial and distal proximal contact was made up with the help of cellophane strip. Gingival embrasure was prepared by the application of standard dental wedges. Final light curing, shaping, polishing and finishing were done by standard ways. The fiber Reinforced Composite full veneer crown was polished by standard composite plastic polisher and light cure bonding agent.

Cementation: The inside of the crown of Fiber Reinforced Composite (FRC) was sand blasted with aluminum oxide. The internal surface was then treated with a bonding agent and delivered with a low viscosity, hybrid, and composite luting agents. These luting agents were bonded to the inside of the crown to the etched dentine and enamel of the abutments.

Procedure of Metal Ceramic crown: The tooth reduction was done in all aspects with ideal procedure. Impression was taken with alginate. Cast was poured with die stone. Die was prepared with ideal method and trimming was done for wax pattern.

Waxing was done with inlay casting wax. Investing and casting were done with standard procedure. Metal framework was tried in for proper fit. Porcelain was bonded over metal framework. Porcelain bonded prostheses was trailed. Final polishing and glazing was done. Cementation was done with Glass-ionomer luting cement.

Instruction was given to the patients and advised them to report after 4 months, 8 months and 12 months interval. Esthetic status was indexed after California Dental Association's quality evaluation system¹⁹.

Marginal adaptation

Grade I: No visible evidence of a crevice along margin into which explorer will penetrate.

Grade II: Visible evidence of slight marginal discrepancy with no evidence of decay; repair can be made or is unnecessary.

Grade III: Discoloration on the margin between the restoration and the tooth structure.

Initial Photograph

Fiber Adaptation

Incremental Composite Buildup

After Cementation of FRC

Data Collection: Data were collected from the patients who attended to report their prostheses condition after 4 months, 8 months and 12 months.

Data analysis: All the collected data were compiled on a master chart first. After coding and editing, the collected data were analyzed by using statistical package for social science (SPSS). The result was presented in tables. Chi-square test was done by using Epi Info (version 12). P-value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

The prospective comparative study was conducted among the patients who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. The patients who attended in the out patient department of Prosthodontics, faculty of Dentistry at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU), from January 2007 to December 2008 were included in this study, among them, 30 were in group- A (experimental), were treated with Fiber Reinforced Composite crown and another 30 were in group- B (control), were treated with Metal ceramic crown.

The observation was done after 4 months, 8 months and 12 months interval of the cementation of crowns and data were collected for selected variables of marginal adaptation of prostheses. Collected data were presented in tabular form and statistical analysis was done to observe the statistical significance.

Table I: Distribution of patients by age (n=60)

Age (years)	Group A (n=30)		Group B (n=30)	
	f	%	f	%
	≤20	6	20.0	6
21 – 30	18	60.0	19	63.3
31 – 40	5	16.7	5	16.7
> 40	1	3.3	0	0.0
Mean ± SD	24.9	±5.8	25.0	±4.8

The table I shows the distribution of patients of both the study groups. The age of patients ranged between 18 and 42 years in group A and 17 and 38 years in group B. The highest number of patients was in the age group 21-30 years in both the groups. The mean age was 24.9±5.8 years and 25.0±4.8 years in group A and group B respectively.

Table II: Distribution of patients by sex (n=60)

Sex	Group A (n=30)		Group B (n=30)		p value
	f	%	f	%	
	Male	12	40.0	14	
Female	18	60.0	16	53.3	

There were 26 male and 34 female patients in the study groups and male female ratio was 1:1.3. In group A patients, 12(40.0%) were male and 18(60.0%) female. In group B 14(46.7%) were male and 16(53.3%) were female. The difference was not statistically significant (p>0.05).

Table III : Distribution of patients according to marginal adaptation of full veneer crown after 4 months (n=60)

Marginal adaptation	Group A (n=30)		Group B (n=30)		p value
	f	%	f	%	
	Grade – I	30	100	30	
Grade – II	0	0.0	0	0.0	
Grade – III	0	0.0	0	0.0	

The table III shows the distribution of patients according to marginal adaptation of full veneer crown. After 4 months all patients were in grade I in both groups.

Table IV: Distribution of patients according to marginal adaptation of full veneer crown after 8 months (n=60)

Marginal adaptation	Group A (n=30)		Group B (n=30)		p value
	f	%	f	%	
	Grade – I	30	100	27	
Grade – II	0	0.0	3	10.0	
Grade – III	0	0.0	0	0.0	

The table IV shows the distribution of patients according to marginal adaptation of full veneer crown. After 8 months all patients were in grade I in group A and 27(90.0%) patients were in grade I in group B. The difference was not statistically significant (p>0.05).

Table V: Distribution of patients according to marginal adaptation of full veneer crown (n=60)

Marginal adaptation	Group A (n=30)		Group B (n=30)		p value
	f	%	f	%	
	Grade – I	30	100	25	
Grade – II	0	0.0	5	17.7	
Grade – III	0	0.0	0	0.0	

The table V shows the distribution of patients according to marginal adaptation of full veneer crown. After 12 months all patients were in grade I in group A and 25(83.3%) patients were in grade I in group B. The difference was statistically significant (p<0.05)

Discussion

The prospective comparative study was conducted among the patients who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. The patients who attended in the out patient department of Prosthodontics, faculty of Dentistry

at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU), from January 2007 to December 2008 were included in this study, among them, 30 patients were in group-A, who treated with Fiber Reinforced Composite Crown and another 30 patients were in group-B who were treated with Metal ceramic full veneer crown. The main objective of this study was to compare the effect of Fiber Reinforced Composite Crown and Metal ceramic full veneer crown.

After cementation of Prostheses the patients were requested to come and maintain follow up visits after 4 months, 8 months and 12 months and data were collected according to marginal adaptation of the prostheses.

The age ranged of both groups was from 17 to 41 years. The highest number of patients was in the age of 21-30 years in both the groups. In this study out of 60 patients, 26 were male and 34 were female and male female ratio was 1:1.3.

Marginal adaptation was examined in accordance with the California Dental Association's (CDA)¹⁹ quality evaluation system described above (materials and methods). According to marginal adaptation after 4, 8 and 12 months it showed that all the patients of group -A were in grade -I i.e. excellent. After 4 months all the patients of group -B were also in grade -I and after 8 and 12 months 27(90.0%) and 25(83.3%) patients were in grade-I in group B. The marginal adaptation of Fiber Reinforced Composite crown was better than Metal ceramic crown .The difference was not statistically significant ($p>0.05$) after 8 months, however after 12 months the difference was significant ($p<0.026$).

Cho et al (2003)²⁰ evaluated the marginal adaptation of FRC crowns with respect to the various types of finish lines. Forty crowns were prepared with different finish lines. The marginal adaptation of crowns with a shoulder finish line was significantly better than crowns with a chamfer finish line before and after cementation ($P<.001$).

Previous study²¹ on effect of Fiber reinforced composite in fixed partial denture (FPD) was conducted in the Department of Prosthodontics at BSMMU, among forty were patients divided into two groups. In that study it was shown that there were no change in esthetic status and no attrition of opposing teeth. Only 2(10.0%) patients were found to chip out composites. Fiber reinforced composite fixed partial denture is an innovative alternative to conventional metal ceramic fixed partial denture.

Conclusion

The Fiber Reinforced Composite crown is a valuable development in the field of Prosthetic Dentistry. This study shows that Fiber reinforced composite crown provides a life like esthetical appearance, better fracture resistance, good marginal adaptation and no attrition of opposite teeth as well as it is a time saving restoration, easy to repair and cost effective.

Recommendations

Within the limitations of this study it is strongly recommended that Dentists can use Fiber Reinforced Composite crown to ensure esthetically pleasant and durable restorations.

The following recommendations are put forward for establishment of the procedure:

- a) The study should be conducted on a long term basis. A larger period of observations is required to test the hypothesis.
- b) As it is a technique sensitive restoration, proper curing and high strength composites should be used to increase the longevity of the prostheses.
- c) The study conducted only at BSMMU among a small group of patients, further study with a large sample size should be done for better conclusion of this result.

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Tooth brushing with and without Dentifrice - A Comparative Study

L Pathak

Abstract

Tooth brushing is such a familiar process that it is easy to forget how crucial it is to oral health and how important it is to brush properly. Twenty three patients were selected in the age-group of 30-40 having tooth brushing abrasion in the cervical region of at least three teeth and taught the Modified Stillman's Brushing Technique during a four week pre-test period. Plaque disclosing agent was used prior to and after brushing to educate the subjects. At the end of the pre-test period a complete oral prophylaxis was done to obtain a 'zero' plaque score. The patient was asked to refrain from any oral hygiene procedure for next 48 hours and nonfibrous regular diet was advised. After 48 hours pre-brushing plaque scoring was recorded according to Turesky-Gilmore-Glickman Modification of the Quigley-Hein plaque index. A split mouth design was followed to record the post brushing plaque scores. Each time the patients were asked to brush on both upper and lower quadrants of one side for recording post-brushing plaque scores 'without dentifrice' first and then brush on the upper and lower quadrants of the other side for recording plaque scores 'with dentifrice'. The three treatment groups viz. Pre-brushing, Post-brushing without dentifrice and Post-brushing with dentifrice when subjected to ANOVA confirmed that the Modified Stillman's Technique effectively removes plaque in both post-brushing situations ($p < 0.01$). The subjects showed a reduction in plaque levels in the Post-brushing trials as indicated by C.D. value (0.0179) ($p < 0.05$). It can be derived from the statistical analysis that if properly done tooth brushing removes plaque effectively when used with or without dentifrice.

Keywords: Toothbrush, Tooth brushing, Modified Stillman's Technique.

Introduction

Procedures for control of supragingival plaque are as old as recorded history of Mankind. Charaka Samhita stressed the importance of tooth brushing and oral hygiene in ancient India. The first patent for a manual toothbrush was issued to Wadsworth in the middle of the 19th Century. A manual toothbrush is a device composed of a shaft with either natural or synthetic bristles at one end intended to remove adherent plaque and food debris from the teeth surfaces to reduce tooth decay¹. Unbeknown to most users the toothbrush is a medical device regulated under the Food, Drug and Cosmetic Act and Regulated Laws 1992². Till now no such toothpaste currently available is accepted by The American Dental Association as ideal for prevention of gingivitis. Indeed tooth brushing with toothpaste was found to be responsible for a high degree of cervical abrasion³. Many variables like brushing technique, duration and frequency of brushing and type of particular filament stiffness may cause cervical abrasion to a large extent⁴⁻⁷.

If used correctly brushing can remove plaque from tooth surface without a dentifrice⁸. Cleaning efficacy of different brushing techniques have been reported in many studies⁹. It is observed that Modified Stillman's Tooth brushing has been the technique of choice for a very few trials. This technique is seen to take care of the teeth and gingiva of the individuals who already developed cervical abrasion due to improper brushing technique. The present study aims to evaluate and compare the cleaning efficacy of the Modified Stillman's Tooth brushing Technique in the individuals who are not exposed to proper brushing and has already developed cervical abrasions.

Methodology

For the purpose of the study twenty three patients who had never received any professional dental care were recruited from the fourth grade employees of the University Hospital.

Exclusion Criteria

Every patient was selected only in the age group of 30-40 and those who had periodontal therapy in the past were excluded from the study. Those having crowding, faulty restorations and any systemic disease were excluded. All the twenty three patients presented at least three teeth together with cervical abrasion.

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Armamentarium used in the study

A detailed medical and dental history was taken from each patient participating in the study. Mouth mirrors, tweezers, kidney tray, dappen dish, mouth mask, gauze strips, ultrasonic scaler, airtor handpiece, rubber cups and pumice powder, medium textured toothbrushes, dentifrice containing one thousand PPM of fluoride, acrylic models for demonstration of brushing technique, looking mirrors and disclosing solution (erythrocin dye) was used for the study.

Pre-Test Period

At the beginning of the study written consent was obtained from all the patients. A complete oral prophylaxis was given to each of them to eliminate the interference of stain and calculus deposits in the grading of plaque. A four week pre-test period followed the oral prophylaxis during which the subjects were taught the importance of the oral physiotherapy programme by incorporating the prescribed tooth brushing technique. Each patient was taught the "Modified Stillmans Technique" of tooth brushing on acrylic models. They were given looking mirrors and plaque disclosing solutions to see the plaque removal prior to and after brushing. The brushing technique was demonstrated in the following way.

Modified Stillman's Technique

A. Position the brush

1. Filaments. Direct the filaments apically.
2. Place side of the brush on the attached gingival.

B. Strokes

1. Place to flex the filaments. The sides of the filaments are pressed lightly against the gingiva. The gingiva will blanch under pressure.
2. Angle the filaments. Turn the handle by rotating the wrist so that the filaments are directed at an angle of approximately 45° with the long axis of the tooth.
3. Activate the brush with a slight vibratory motion. The tips of the filaments should touch the gingival with a light pressure.
4. Roll and vibrate the brush while working slowly down over the gingival and tooth. Make some of the filaments reach interdental.

C. Replace Brush for Repeat strokes.

D. Repeat Strokes for each two quadrants.

Steps A through C was repeated in two quadrants (upper and lower) of the same side at a time. The time allotted was 2 minutes and 3 minutes for each side (right and left) for different sessions. The two quadrants of the same side was scored after brushing for 2 mins. and 3 mins. and also with and without dentifrice.

E. Position brush for anterior lingual and palatal surfaces the long, narrow way and repeat the strokes as in B.

F. Occlusal Brushing

1. Place brush on occlusal surface of molar teeth with filament tips pointed into the occlusal pits at a right angle. The handle should be parallel with the occlusal surface. The toe of the brush should cover the distal groove of the most posterior tooth.
2. Vibrate the brush in a slight circular movement, while maintaining the filament tips on the occlusal surface. Press moderately so that the filaments do not bend but go straight into the pits and fissures.
3. Move brush to the premolar area, overlapping previous brush position repeat 1 and 2 steps.

Experimental Procedure

At the end of the pre-test period i.e. on day 0 the patient was called.

Day 0

Every subject was comfortably seated on a dental chair. Rubber cup polishing was done with pumice powder. Then the subject was asked to keep the disclosing solution in mouth for one minute. Any amount of plaque disclosed was removed by scaling and polishing until 'zero' plaque score was obtained. Thereafter the subject was asked to refrain from any oral hygiene procedure without fibrous diet for next 48 hours.

Day 1

After 48 hours the subject reported to the clinic. The subject was asked to swiss the solution (1:50 dilution) inside mouth for 2 minutes. This was followed by a thorough rinse with plain water to remove any excess of the disclosing solution. A split-mouth design was followed and Pre-brushing plaque score was recorded in all the four quadrants according to Turesky-Gilmore-Glickman modification of the Quigley-Hein plaque index as described before. This established the amount of plaque formed during the 48 hours period while the subject refrained from any oral hygiene measures to serve as baseline control.

After the pre-brushing scoring the subject was given a toothbrush (medium textured) and was asked to brush the teeth for two minutes on the two quadrants of the same side (both maxillary and mandibular) without any dentifrice. Following brushing the plaque was disclosed and post-brushing plaque data 'without dentifrice' for two minutes was recorded. Thereafter the subject was asked to put an approximately 1/3rd of an inch length of dentifrice on the bristles and brush on the other two remaining quadrants in the opposite side for two minutes. The post-brushing plaque score 'with dentifrice' for two minutes was recorded.

After a gap of another week the subjects were recalled and the experimental procedure was repeated from Day-0 to Day-1 but this time the test quadrants were reversed for recording the data in the post brushing scoring for the same duration i.e. two minutes.

Again after a gap of one week the subjects were recalled. Procedure from Day-0 to Day-1 was repeated but this time the subjects brushed for three minutes duration for each quadrants of the same side. The post-brushing data recorded for both with and without dentifrice. After one week the subjects were recalled for repeat sessions from Day-0 to Day-1. The brushing time was three minutes and the post-brushing data was recorded by reversing the quadrants. All the data were collected by a single examiner (self).

Results and observations

Twenty three subjects participated in this clinical study. A splitmouth design was followed to record all the data. A plaque index was calculated for each subject as follows:

$$PI = \frac{\text{total plaque score}}{\text{no. of tooth surfaces}}$$

The pre-brushing PI = the amount of plaque measured before tooth brushing

The post-brushing PI (with toothpaste and without toothpaste) = the amount of plaque measured after tooth brushing.

A mean plaque index (MPI) was calculated as follows:

$$MPI = \text{Mean} \pm \text{S.E. (Standard Error)}$$

The experimental data obtained were subjected to statistical analysis. The mean age of all the subjects was 33 years. For the purpose of comparison between the plaque levels at different situations the following were considered as different treatment groups:

- Pre-brushing plaque levels at 2 mins.
- Pre-brushing plaque levels at 3 mins.
- Post-brushing with dentifrice plaque levels at 2 mins.
- Post-brushing with dentifrice plaque levels at 3 mins.
- Post-brushing without dentifrice plaque levels at 2 mins.
- Post-brushing without dentifrice plaque levels at 3 mins.

Table I shows the distribution of plaque scores recorded as per Turesky-Gilmore-Glickman modification of the Quigley-Hein plaque index. Table II shows a decrease in the plaque levels for all the post-brushing MPIs. Table III shows that the t-values in all the treatment groups bear no statistical significance when brushing time was increased from 2 mins. to 3 mins. Table IV shows the values of three treatment groups after ANOVA was done. This analysis confirmed that Modified Stillman's Technique effectively removes plaque in both post-brushing treatment groups ($p < 0.01$).

Table V shows the various plaque levels and their p-values. Here treatment groups shown as having same superscript do not differ significantly. The post-brushing data in both situations as indicated in the C.D. value (0.0179) is significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table I : Distribution of Subjects by Plaque Score

Score	Pre -Brushing		Post -Brushing (With)		Post -Brushing (Without)	
	2	3	2	3	2	3
0	0	0	764	833	735	790
1	154	130	476	441	482	459
2	892	886	104	70	127	95
3	1337	1393	0	0	0	0
4	295	265	0	0	0	0
5	10	14	0	0	0	0

Table II : Split Mouth Data Comparison of Mean Plaque Index for the Two Treatment with Controlled Baseline

	Pre -Brushing (Controlled Baseline)		Post -Brushing (With Dentifrice)		Post -Brushing (Without Dentifrice)	
	2	3	2	3	2	3
Mpi	2.680	2.711	0.5183	0.4319	0.5592	0.4785
	± 0.065	± 0.061	± 0.031	± 0.023	± 0.034	± 0.028

Table III : Values Shown After T-Test for the three Different Situations

t-Value			
Treatment Groups			
	Pre-Brushing (Controlled Baseline)	Post-Brushing (With Dentifrice)	Post-Brushing (Without Dentifrice)
t-Value	0.23	1.538	1.059
d.f.	44	44	44
Statistical Significance	NS	NS	NS

Table IV : Reduction in Plaque Levels by Modified Stillman’s Tooth brushing Technique (Anova)

Sources of variation	d.f.	S.S.	M.S.	F
Treatment	2	2996.61147	148.30577	1631.526
Error	273	24.81269	0.0909	
Total	275	321.427766		

(p<0.01)

d.f = Degrees of freedom

S.S = sum of squares

M.S = Mean sum of squares

F = Variance Ratio

Table V : Comparison of Plaque Levels of the Three Treatment Groups And Their P-Value

Treatment Groups	Plaque levels	P-Value
Pre -Brushing (Controlled Baseline)	2.695 ^a ± 0.063	P<0.05 (C.D. = 0.0871)
Post -Brushing (With Dentifrice)	0.4751 ^b ± 0.027	
Post -Brushing (Without Dentifrice)	0.5188 ^b ± 0.031	

N.B. : Treatment groups having same superscript do not differ significantly

Discussion

Promotion of oral health and prevention of oral diseases have been the focus of oral hygiene practice since its inception. In our country social and economic conditions have deprived a large section of people an adequate oral health practice. There are many tooth brushing studies which will remove plaque effectively without harmful effect on hard & soft tissues¹⁰⁻¹². The Modified Stillman’s tooth brushing technique fairly works well for patients with tooth brushing abrasions as well as anatomically normal gingiva. In our endeavor to study the effectiveness of this brushing technique we evaluated the treatment groups in different situations. The data showed that all the 23 individuals accumulated a minimum level of plaque (score 1).The score of 3 was obtained in maximum no. of pre-brushing situations both at 2 & 3 minutes. A small no. of individuals accumulated the maximum plaque level (score 5) during 48 hours of oral hygiene abstinence.

It was noted that the post brushing treatment groups (with or without dentifrice) did not differ significantly as seen in table III. The emphasis is to be given on the method how the brush is employed and not on the abrasive action of the dentifrice. In the present study a split mouth design once followed whereby two quadrants (upper and lower) were brushed alternatively with and without dentifrice to observe the reduction in plaque levels. In both the situations a significant reduction in plaque levels was observed ($p < 0.05$). The Modified Stillman's brushing technique seems to be an ideal oral hygiene practice which does not necessitate the use of toothpaste always.

Conclusion

Tooth brushing is a simple mechanical measure which can be easily taught as individual home oral therapy programme. It is necessary to find out which technique the patient can perform best. It is useless to insist on a technique which the patient finds difficult and ends up having cervical abrasions. Indeed, manual dexterity does not necessarily go with intellect and some of the brightest patient's prove to be extremely in compliant when it comes to cleaning the teeth. Regular guidance and encouragement are essential for people to develop the necessary skill. Most of the people engage in faulty brushing which in the course of time results in tooth brushing abrasions. Modified Stillman's Technique of brushing may be incorporated as the preferred technique of choice for the overall maintenance of health of gingiva and the teeth.

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Oral Health Status among Drug Addicts in a Selected Hospital in Dhaka City

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Abstract

This was a cross-sectional study on oral health status of drug addicted patients admitted in a drug abuse treatment center in Dhaka city. This study was conducted at Mukti Mental Hospital, Drug & Alcohol Treatment Center situated at Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh. The study was carried out among 50 drug addicts from the month of January to June 2012. Data were collected from the patients from 21st April to 5th May 2012. The main objective of the study was to assess and investigate the oral hygiene practice and oral health status of drug abusers. Fifty drug abusers irrespective of sex and age were interviewed & their oral health status was evaluated using the World Health Organization recommended procedures for Decayed, Missing, Filled teeth and the periodontal status. Data were collected with a pretested structured questionnaire and checklist. Dental caries was found in 92% of the drug addicts, while Missing and Filled teeth were recorded 86% and 88% of the addicts respectively. 86% of the addicts demonstrated DMFT score 1 or Higher; whereas 14% of the addicts demonstrated DMFT score 0 or were free from any form of dental decay, missing teeth or dental filling and 74% of the drug addicts had gingival inflammation and bleeding from gum, 42% had some oral mucosal lesion like aphthous ulcer and candidiasis. The number of Decayed, Missing or Filled teeth increased with less frequency of daily tooth brushing and this finding was significant ($p < 0.01$). On the basis of these findings it was concluded that dental caries in drug addicts is a major health concern and creating awareness among the public about harmful effects of drugs on their oral health through plan and policy can reduce the burden of dental diseases. Moreover mass media and general education of the mass people can play a vital role.

Keywords: Oral health status, Drug addicts.

Introduction

A public health approach to drug addiction should include preventing initiation of use, facilitating addiction cessation, and promoting abstinence from all kinds of drug by current users.

Addiction is a chronic, relapsing disorder characterized by compulsion to take a drug and loss of self-control in limiting drug intake.¹

The substances or drugs may be natural or synthetic, the use of which has a psychoactive effect and alters or modifies the functions of a living organism. Globally, the number of drug abusers in 2007 was 200 million, i.e. 4.8% of the global population.² In the latest reports with regards to Indian context, 11.35 million persons were addicted to drugs.³ In Bangladesh the number of drug abusers is about 2 millions.

Drugs commonly abused are narcotics (including poppy, opium, morphine, codeine, heroin, brown sugar, opioids, meperidine, pethidine, and methadone), cannabis (marijuana, hashish, and dried parts of cannabis plant), stimulants (amphetamines, cocaine), hallucinogens (LSD, phencyclidine, mescaline, and psilocybin), depressants (barbiturates and benzodiazepines), and miscellaneous (antihistaminics, solvents in aerosols, glue, and whitening fluid).⁴ In Bangladesh gull, sada pata, jorda, guzza, phensidil, yaba, bangla mod has been traditionally known. In India, the abuse of alcohol, cannabis, and raw opium has been traditionally known; while the abuse of synthetic narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances is comparatively a new phenomenon.⁴

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Studies have shown that the dental health and oral health are affected by drug abuse.⁵⁻⁹ Concomitant use of psychotropic substances such as tobacco, alcohol and areca nut further deteriorates the health status of the individual. Drugs abused adversely affect the oral soft and hard tissues (dental caries, periodontitis) or may lead to potentially malignant states (leukoplakia, oral submucous fibrosis) or may predispose to oral infections (candidiasis, gingivitis) by compromising local immunity.¹⁰ Description of the oral health status of drug addicts in Bangladeshi drug abuse treatment centers need sparse, a cross sectional study was performed to ascertain the status of oral health among drug addicts.

Materials and Methods

This study was a cross-sectional study. The study was carried out at Mukti Madokashokti Niramoy Kendro at Gulshan-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Total allocated study period was 6 months commencing from January to June 2012. 50 addicted patients irrespective of age and sex admitted at the centre were selected for the study. Purposive sampling technique was used.

Data were collected by the researcher himself through observation; interview of the addicted patients and by clinical examination of the oral cavity after taking verbal consent of the patients.

Data analysis was done using statistical software Statistical Package for Social Science or SPSS for Windows version and Microsoft Excel according to the key variables and objectives of the study.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of the addicts according to occurrence of bleeding from gum during tooth brushing (n=50)

Occurrence of bleeding from gum	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	37	74
No	13	26
Total	50	100

Table 1- shows that majority of drug addicts 37(74%) had bleeding from gum, while 13(26%) drug addicts had no bleeding.

Table 2: Distribution of the drug addicts by the number of decayed teeth (n=50)

Number of decayed teeth	Frequency	Percentage
None	5	10
1	7	14
2	5	10
3	11	22
4	9	18
>4	13	26
Total	50	100

Table 2- shows that among drug addicts 10% had decayed free teeth, 7(14.%) had only 1 tooth decay, 5(10%) had 2 teeth decay, 11(22%) had 3 teeth decay, 9(18%) had 4 teeth decay, while 13(26%) had more than 4 teeth decayed.

Table 3: Distribution of the drug addicts by oral mucosal lesion (n=50)

Presence of oral mucosal lesion	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	21	42
No	29	58
Total	50	100

Table 3- shows that among drug addicts 21(42%) had oral mucosal lesion, while 29(58%) had no any oral mucosal lesion.

Table 4: Distribution of the drug addicts by gingival inflammation (n=50)

Presence of gingival inflammation	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	37	74
No	13	26
Total	50	100

Table 4- Shows that among drug addicts 37 (74%) had gingival inflammation, while 13 (26%) did not have any gingival inflammation

Table 5: Distribution of drug addicts by the number of missing teeth (n=50)

Number of missing teeth	Frequency	Percentage
None	7	14
1	12	24
2	5	10
3	9	18
4	17	34
Total	50	100

Table 5- shows that among drug addicts 7 (14%) did not have any missing tooth, 12(24%) had only 1 tooth missing, 5(10%) had 2 teeth missing, 9 (18%) had 3 teeth missing, 17(34%) had 4 teeth missing

Table 6: Distribution of drug addicts by the number of filled teeth (n=50)

Number of filled teeth	Frequency	Percentage
None	6	12
1	13	26
2	8	16
3	11	22
4	12	24

Table 6- shows that among 50 addicts 6(12%) did not have any filled tooth, 23(46%) had only 1 tooth filled, 8(16%) had 2 teeth filled, 11(22%) had 3 teeth filled, 12(24%) had 4 teeth filled.

Table 7: Distribution of the drug addicts according to DMFT score (n=50)

DMFT score	Frequency	Percentage
0	7	14
=>1	43	86
Total	50	100

Table 7- shows that among drug addicts 7 (14%) had DMFT score 0, while 43 (86%) had DMFT score 1 or above.

Discussion

While several studies reported regarding dental diseases and oral hygiene practice in Bangladesh population, there is no documented information about drug abusers' oral health status. This paper therefore, provides background information on the status of oral health among a group of drug abusers undergoing rehabilitation at a major narcotic detoxification center in Bangladesh. Fifty drug abusers irrespective of sex and age were interviewed & their oral health status was evaluated using the World Health Organization recommended procedures for Decayed, Missing, Filled teeth and the periodontal status and by oral mucosal lesion & gingival inflammation. Data were collected with a pretested structured questionnaire and checklist. Dental caries was found in 92% of the drug addicts, while Missing and Filled teeth were recorded 86% and 88% of the addicts respectively. 86% of the addicts demonstrated DMFT score 1 or Higher; whereas 14% of the addicts demonstrated DMFT score 0 or were free from any form of dental decay, missing teeth or dental filling and 74% of the drug addicts had gingival inflammation and bleeding from gum, 42% had some oral mucosal lesion like apthous ulcer and candidiasis. The number of Decayed, Missing or Filled teeth increased with less frequency of daily tooth brushing and this finding was significant ($p < 0.01$). On the basis of these findings it was concluded that dental caries in drug addicts is a major health concern and creating awareness among the public about harmful effects of drugs on their oral health through plan and policy can reduce the burden of dental diseases.

Conclusion

This study found an increase in the rate of caries with increasing duration and frequency of using drugs. Male seems to suffer more from dental decay in comparison to female because number of addicts in male are more than female. The overall oral health status of addicts was not possible to ascertain because of some limitations, but the high rate of dental caries definitely portrays poor oral health among them. It is not to be forgotten that oral health is a component of general health and oral health status may be considered to represent the level of health care of a nation. So initiative should be taken to improve the oral health through appropriate measures.

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Periodontal Cosmetic Surgery - Concept of Gingival Depigmentation

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Abstract

A smile is more than a method of communication and is a means of socialization and attraction. The harmony of the smile is determined not only by the shape, the position and the color of the teeth but also by the gingival tissues. Gingival pigmentation is well documented in the literature and is considered to be multifactorial. This problem aggravates in patients with gummy smile. There are various treatment modalities for managing this quality of life hampering, esthetic problem including chemical, surgical, cryotherapy, radiotherapy, not the least LASER. The most important factor for determining the treatment for gingival melanin pigmentation is the type of pigmentation, patient acceptance of treatment procedure, its prevalence and its esthetic importance depending on the skin complexion of the patient.

Key words: *Gingiva, Depigmentation, Esthetics, Physiologic pigmentation, Melanin.*

Introduction

A smile expresses a feeling of joy, success, sensuality, affection and reveals self-confidence and kindness. Gingival health and appearance are essential components of an attractive smile. Oral melanin pigmentation is well documented in the literature and is considered to be multifactorial, whether physiological/pathological and can be caused by a variety of local and or systemic factors.¹

Classification

Dummett and Barrens (1971) in their review divided oromucosal pigmentation in the following categories.²

- I Local and ethnic pigmentations
- II Oral pigmentation manifestations of systemic diseases
- III Pigmentation disturbances associated with pharmaceutical and other chemicals
- IV Benign and malignant neoplasms of pigmentation origin.

Gingival melanin pigmentation is measured using the following index.

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Gingival pigmentation index: (Dummett Oral Pigmentation index DOPI³)

Score 0: Absence of any pigmentation

Score 1: Spots of brown to black pigmentation

Score 2: Localized brown to black pigmentation (not diffuse)

Score 3: Diffuse brown to black pigmentation (diffuse involving marginal and attached gingiva)

Gingival melanin pigmentation of the gingiva is completely benign and does not present a medical problem, but patients may complain that their black gums are unaesthetic. This problem aggravates in patients with a "gummy smile" or excessive gingival display while smiling or talking.^{4,5,6}

The smile lines can be analyzed according to the following classification⁷.

Class 1: Very high smile line -more than 2 mm of the marginal gingiva visible or more than 2 mm apical to the cemento-enamel junction visible for the reduced but healthy periodontium. This could be "gummy smile".

Class 2: High smile line - between 0 and 2 mm of marginal gingiva visible or between 0 and 2 mm apical to the cemento-enamel junction visible for the reduced but healthy periodontium.

Class 3: Average smile line- only gingival embrasures visible.

Class 4: Low smile line- gingival embrasures and cemento-enamel junction not visible.

Report of the Case

A female patient of 22 years of age reported with a chief complaint of dark gums and which exposed during smiling and talking. Dark gingiva and gummy smile was affecting the social life and in a greater way her quality of life. After complete evaluating her medical history and preliminary investigation it was diagnosed as racial pigmentation. Melanin pigmentation is a physiological pigmentation. We planned for surgical scalpel method for depigmentation.

Fig 1: Pre Operative

Fig 2: Per-Operative

Fig 3: Post Operative

Various Other Methods Used

	Gingival abrasion	Split thickness excision technique	Free gingival graft	Cryosurgery	LASER
Local anesthesia	Required	Required	Required	Not required	Not usually
Technique	Non invasive	Invasive	Invasive	Non invasive	Non invasive
Ease of performing	Technique sensitive	Technique sensitive	Technique sensitive	Technique sensitive	Relatively easy
Discomfort/pain	Minimal	Minimal	Mild to moderate	No discomfort	Pricking pain
Periodontal dressing	Necessary	Necessary	Necessary	Not necessary	Not necessary
Healing	1-2 weeks	1-2 weeks	2-3 weeks	Within a week	Within a week
Final appearance	Papillary gingiva shows pigmentation	Complete	Ghost like appearance (Hypopigmented areas)	Complete depigmentation	Complete depigmentation
Repigmentation	Seen (9 months)	Not seen (duration can vary from 33 to 120 days)	Not seen	Recurrence 1-3 months	Not seen
Cost	Cost effective	Cost effective	Cost effective	Expensive	Cost effective

Chemical methods:

Most commonly used are phenols and alcohol. The treatment was not acceptable to the clinicians or the patients. In 1951 Hirschfield and Hirschfield⁸ used a mixture of phenol (90%) and alcohol (95%) to burn out the pigmented gingiva by destroying tissue down to and slightly below the basal layer of the mucous membranes.

Ascorbic acid (AS-G gel) was used by Yashuko *et al* for depigmentation and found that it significantly inhibited tyrosinase activity and melanin formation in B16 mouse melanoma cells. They concluded that AS-G has potential for the treatment of gingival melanin pigmentation.

Surgical methods:

1. *Gingival abrasion technique*

In this technique a medium grit football shaped diamond bur is used at high speeds to denude the epithelium. The procedure requires 45 min to 1 h for completion. Procedural discomfort, placement of periodontal pack, duration of procedure, recurrence of pigmentation and technique sensitivity are few of the drawbacks of this procedure.

2. *Scalpel surgical technique or split thickness epithelial excision technique*

This procedure essentially involves surgical removal⁹ of gingival epithelium along with a layer of the underlying connective tissue and allowing the denuded connective tissue to heal by secondary intention. Delicate scarring, exposure of the alveolar bone at areas where the gingiva is thin and repigmentation can be few of the disadvantages of the procedure¹⁰.

3. *Free gingival grafting*

Described by Tamizi, Taheri (1996)¹¹ for treating severe physiologic melanin pigmentation requires replacement with an unpigmented free gingival autograft. The result of this procedure showed no evidence of repigmentation even after 4.5 years.

4. *Acellular dermal matrix allograft*

Acellular dermal matrix with partial thickness flap has been used in the elimination of gingival melanin pigmentation. It can be a substitute for gingival autograft¹².

Lasers:

Lasers have become widely used in medicine and surgery since the development of the Ruby laser by Maiman in 1960. Laser ablation for gingival depigmentation has been recognized as one of the most effective, pleasant, and reliable techniques. Different lasers have been used for gingival depigmentation, including Carbon dioxide (CO₂) (10,600 nm), Diode (820 nm), Neodymium-doped:

Yttrium, Aluminum, and Garnet (Nd:YAG) (1064 nm), Erbium (Er)-doped:YAG (2940 nm) and Erbium- and chromium-doped: yttrium, scandium, gallium, garnet (Er, Cr: YSGG) (2780 nm) lasers.

Cryosurgical procedure:

The dose of cryogen and the choice of delivery method depend on the size, tissue type, and depth of the lesion. The area of the body on which the lesion is located and the required depth of freeze also should be considered. Additional patient factors to consider includes the thickness of the epidermis and underlying structures, the water content of the skin, and local blood-flow¹³.

1. Dipstick method
2. Spray technique
3. Cryoprobe technique

Radiosurgery:

Radiosurgery uses a 4 MHz radio signal to produce a fine microsmooth incision with no overt lateral heat being sent to the surrounding tissues. A superficial effect is sufficient to remove pigmentations. Touching the pigmented areas lightly with the No. 135 ball shaped electrode or tapping the area with the No. 134 L-shaped electrode when the Ellman Surgitron or Radiolase II is operating will successfully treat a case with gingival melanin pigmentation. This method at least required two sittings for completion within 2 weeks of treatment¹⁴.

Conclusion

Based on the available literature gingival melanin pigmentation can vary depending on whether it is physiological or pathological, based on the location, color or it can be traumatic. The most important factor for determining the treatment for gingival melanin pigmentation is the type of pigmentation, patient acceptance of treatment procedure, its prevalence and its esthetic importance depending on the skin complexion of the patient.

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Orthopantomographic evaluation of third molar developmental stages in relation to chronological age of Bangladeshi female garment workers

SZ Mahmud¹, NA Nomann², MA Kabir³, CM Jan⁴

Abstract

Human teeth are among the most distinctive and long lasting features of mammal species. Various quantitative and qualitative methodologies have been developed by the researchers in order to establish an assessment format to determine the correlation between the dental age and the chronological age. The morphological and radiological examinations of third molars make up a part of the orthodontic, pedodontic, forensic odontology and oral surgical treatments and remain the most reliable biologic indicator available for age estimation during the middle teens and early twenties. This age calculation requirement is not only for differentiating the juvenile from the adult status in criminal law cases, but also for chronological age estimation in relation to school attendance, social benefits, employment and marriage. A case for actual need for age estimation using a developing third molar is presented here.

Key words: Age estimation, Chronological age, Dental age, Tooth development, Third molar.

Introduction

Growth is an essential feature of life of a child that distinguishes him or her from an adult. Growth denotes a net increase in the size or mass of tissues, whereas development specifies maturation of functions. Hereditary, functional, environmental, nutritional, sexual, metabolic, social, emotional, cultural factors affect growth and development greatly.¹

In advanced countries various quantitative and qualitative methodologies have been developed by the researchers in order to establish an assessment format to determine the correlation between the dental age and the chronological age. By the chronological age we mean the age of an individual in years while by the dental age we mean the age of an individual determined by the dentition.² However, the relationship between growth and chronological age is not linear and therefore the concept of 'biological' age is used which maybe expressed as either skeletal age or dental age. When the birth date is not known, there will be a strong need to estimate the biological or dental age.³ Over the last few years, age evaluation of live subjects has become very important in forensic sciences. People with incorrect birth certificates often need age estimation procedures to obtain regular documents. In adoption cases, it is frequently necessary to develop age estimation procedures to fulfill the purpose of the process. In criminal circumstances, lack of documents to confirm chronological age may have important consequences.⁴ This is surprising since, in criminal law a need exists to separate the juvenile from adult status for individuals lacking age documentation. Specifically around 18 years of age, all permanent teeth have completed their root formation and show closed apices, except for the third molars. These teeth, if present, offer the only possibility for dental age estimation between 16 and 22 years of age.⁵ This age calculation requirement is not only for differentiating the juvenile from the adult status in criminal law cases, but also for chronological age estimation in relation to school attendance, social benefits, employment and marriage.⁶

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For the juvenile age group, there are two methods of identification: the morphological examination of skeletal features and radiological examination of the development of third molars. The morphological and radiological examinations of third molars make up a part of the orthodontic, pedodontic and oral surgical treatments and remain the most reliable biologic indicator available for estimation of age during the middle teens and early twenties.⁷ The age assessment methods are relatively simple and involve the identification of the stage of mineralization on radiographic images followed by their comparison with the standard stage to estimate the approximate age range. Various radiographic images that can be used in age identification are intraoral periapical radiographs, lateral oblique radiographs, cephalometric radiographs, panoramic radiographs, digital imaging and advanced imaging technologies.⁸ Several methods of determining the dental age according to the degree of calcification of the permanent teeth as seen in radiographs have been described. Currently, one of the most well-known and widely used methods for estimating dental age is the Demirjian method, first described in 1973 and based on a large sample of French-Canadian children.⁹

Case Report

An 18-years-old female patient was referred from a garment factory to collect medical report on her age determination whether she was 18 years or not. On examination of her teeth, it was observed that all the 3rd molars were clinically absent. As dental x-ray facilities were available, an orthopantomogram (panoramic radiograph) was taken to detect her chronological age based on the dental developmental stages of third molars.

Radiographic examination showed that both the maxillary and mandibular third molar crowns were completed but the roots have not yet been formed (Figure 01). In accordance with the chart of Demirjian *et. al.* (Figure 02) the morphology matched with stage D where the crown formations were completed.¹⁰ This finding was subsequently compared with Table 1 provided by Mincer *et. al.*¹¹ Stage D of mandibular third molars development had a mean age of 16.0 years with a range of 14.36 to 17.64 years at one standard deviation. As the morphology of the tooth formation of the female was in D stage, the probability of this female being 16 years was possible.

Figure 01: Orthopantomographic view of the female garment worker showing the developing third molar.

Figure 02: Schematic drawing of the eight stages of crown - root formation of the molars as proposed by Demirjian *et. al.*¹⁰ Stages A, B, C do not occur in the age group included in this study. Stage D crown formation is completed, stage E the root length is less than the crown height, stage F the root length is equal to or greater than the crown height, stage G the walls of the root canal are parallel and its apical end is still opened and stage H the apical formation is completed.

Table 1: Mean age at attainment of stages of third molar crown-root formation according to Mincer *et. al.*¹¹

Grade of formation		D	E	F	G	H
Maxilla						
Male	$\bar{x}$	16.0	16.6	17.7	18.2	20.2
	sd	1.97	2.38	2.28	1.92	2.09
Female	$\bar{x}$	16.0	16.9	18.0	18.8	20.6
	sd	1.55	1.83	1.95	2.27	2.09
Mandible						
Male	$\bar{x}$	15.5	17.3	17.5	18.3	20.5
	sd	1.59	2.47	2.14	1.93	1.97
Female	$\bar{x}$	16.0	16.9	17.7	19.1	20.9
	sd	1.64	1.75	1.80	2.18	2.01

SD = Standard Deviation
 $\bar{x}$ = Mean Age

Discussion

Dental identification of humans occurs for a number of different reasons and in a number of different situations. The bodies of victims of violent crimes, fires, motor vehicle accidents and work place accidents, can be disfigured to such an extent that identification by a family member is neither reliable nor desirable. Persons who have deceased for some time prior to discovery and those found in water also present unpleasant and difficult visual identifications. Dental identifications have always played a key role in natural and man made disaster situations and in particular the mass casualties normally associated with aviation disasters. Because of the lack of a comprehensive fingerprint database, dental identification continues to be crucial in the United Kingdom.¹²

In July 1993, an unknown murdered male was examined whose facial features, skin color and dentition were suggestive that he was an Indo-European. All the third molar teeth were not present clinically in the deceased during oral examination. The third molars are prone to impaction as they are the last teeth to form and erupt. These teeth erupt when the roots are 3/4 formed. That is the reason why x-rays should be taken during every examination.¹³ Only viable examination method for this purpose is to take an OrthoPantomoGraphic (OPG) x-ray to analyze the development of the third permanent molar (wisdom tooth).¹⁴ In the present case, a panoramic radiograph was also taken to detect her chronological age in relation to dental age.

In between 2006 and 2010 an investigation studied third molar development in 329 orthopantomograms of Portuguese individuals with an age range between 14.0 to 22.8 years, through five different methods (Demirjian, Haavikko, Harris and Nortje, Kullman and Solari) to evaluate the dental development in the ages of Portuguese criminal law: 16 and 18 years old. It represented the probability of an individual in the different stages of dental development be respectively less than 18 years old or at least 16 years old.¹⁵ Similar result was found in the current case indicating that the probability of this female being 16 years was possible.

Table 1 provided in current study was for Caucasoids, which is strongly related to the racial origin of that female garment worker who was a Bangladeshi. However, it is not known if this table is suitable for the Mongoloid population. The stages from E-G there were earlier development in females in maxillary molars but it was earlier in males in mandibular molars. The full eruption of third molar (H stage) was earlier in females in the four molars compared with males.¹⁶

Orthopantomogram (OPG) is very useful for the inspection of child labor. The International Labor Organization (ILO) undertook a study of child worker in the urban informal economy, including the garment sector where it emerged that 70 percent of child workers in the industry were girls and that there was a pattern of informal recruitment, typically around 11 years of age, to do mostly casual jobs. The mean age of these children was 13 years.¹⁷ In 1993, the Government of Bangladesh created a National Labor Law Commission to revise and harmonize labor laws. The first draft of the recommendations, completed on March 31, 1994, proposes to eliminate the inconsistencies regarding the minimum age for employment by defining a child as a person who has not completed his fourteenth year of age.¹⁸ The new law in 2006 prohibits employment of children under 14 years old, as well as hazardous forms of child labor for persons under 18 years of age.¹⁹ In criminal circumstances, lack of documents to confirm chronological age may have important consequences.⁴

Tooth formation has been more widely used than tooth eruption for assessing dental maturation, because it is a continuous and progressive process that can be followed radiographically, and most teeth can be evaluated at each examination. It has been reported that development of each individual can be affected by genetic, racial, nutritional, climatic, hormonal and environmental factors.²⁰ Third molar growth and calcification are definitely not the favourite development marker. However, it is suitable because there are no other favourable indicators during the late teens and early twenties.¹³ In recent years, there has been great interest in the changes of the chemical composition of teeth. It has been reported that aspartic acid in tooth enamel and dentine exhibit increasing racemization with age. This reaction was found to be a good biochronological tool for assessing age and further research is being done in this area.²¹

Conclusion

For medico legal purposes, 18 years of age is an important cut off point. If a subject presents with a developmental stage A to D there is less likelihood that subject is 18 years old. On the other side if subject presents with developmental stage of H, there are more chances that the subject has crossed the 18 years of age. It is important to develop regional age estimation tables based on local surveys mainly considering ages of forensic interest.

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Posterior Resin Bonded Fixed Dental Prosthesis

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Abstract

Dentistry is an ever evolving science. With the advancements in the field of bonding techniques and also in the tooth preparation methods, the use of Resin bonded fixed dental prostheses is becoming a treatment of choice for small posterior edentulous spans.

Key words: Resin cement, Maryland Bridge.

Introduction

Resin-bonded fixed partial dentures (RBFDPs) have undergone a lot many changes over the years. Rochette was the first to describe a Resin Bonded Fixed Partial Denture. Initially Resin-bonded fixed partial dentures (RBFDPs) were suggested for replacing small anterior teeth.¹ Later, improvements in the bonding techniques and innovations in the tooth preparation design permitted even posterior teeth replacements using Resin-bonded fixed partial dentures (RBFDPs). To enhance the attachment of the resin cement to the metal surface, macro mechanical retention such as incorporation of a mesh framework, was suggested initially. Later, electrolytic or chemical etching of the casting was used to produce surface micro roughness.

Currently micromechanical retention through air abrasion with aluminum oxide (50-250 µm), as well as the use of a silicoater is used routinely for inducing surface micro roughness of the metal surface. However, silicoated Fixed Partial Dentures (FPDs) must be cemented within 20 minutes of surface treatment for optimal bonding. The design of Resin-bonded fixed partial dentures (RBFDPs) also went through a number of changes². With a minimal preparation or no preparation of the abutments for limited coverage of the abutments, the preparations gradually became more invasive involving proximal grooves and occlusal or lingual rest seats.

Resin cements used for cementation of Resin-bonded fixed partial dentures (RBFDPs) now a days, have superior capabilities of bonding to base metal alloys and bonding to treated or etched dentin. Whenever debonding occur a predominance of enamel-to-resin bond failure rather than metal-to-resin bond failure is noted. However the enamel-to-resin bond strength can be improved with the incorporation of macro mechanical retentive features in the abutment preparation itself to augment the overall bond.

The prognosis of Resin-bonded fixed partial dentures (RBFDPs) has however been less favorable as compared to a conventional Fixed Partial Dentures (FPDs).

The mean survival rate of Resin-bonded fixed partial dentures (RBFDPs) was as follows: 1 year, 89%; 2 years, 84%; 3 years, 80%; and 4 years, 74%.

Case Report

A 24 year old lady reported to the Department of Prosthodontics in Career Post-Graduate Institute of Dental Sciences (CPGIDS) College, Lucknow, India for replacement of missing left maxillary second premolar (tooth number 25), (Fig. 01). After taking all the local and systemic factors into consideration and weighing all the treatment options, a Resin-bonded fixed partial denture (RBFDP) was opted.

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Fig. 01: Pre treatment, Missing tooth number 25.

Abutment Preparations:

The design of the prosthesis was planned on the diagnostic casts.

Fig. 02: Design of the prosthesis planned on the diagnostic casts. Occlusal rests on 24 and 26 with preparation of the palatal walls along with proximal grooves. An additional occlusal rest was planned on 26.

In addition to the customary proximal and lingual reduction of the abutments, one rest seat was prepared on the occlusal surface of each abutment. Proximal grooves were also prepared (Fig. 02). The facial and lingual walls of these proximal grooves were slightly convergent toward the occlusal surface to provide “undercut retention.” An additional rest seat was prepared on the occlusal surface of the molar. The margins of the preparation were kept supragingival³. After impression making in a silicone impression material provisionally restored with Zinc oxide eugenol cement.

Fig. 03: Addition silicone impression material. Examix NDS (GC-America)

Fig. 04: Impression of the prepared teeth made with putty wash technique.

The casting was designed so that the metal projections from the pontic fit closely into the gingival floors of the occlusal rests. The edentulous space was found to be too wide to accommodate a single premolar and hence the pontic was designed as a molar.

Fig. 05: The completed prosthesis being tried in the patient's mouth.

The Resin-bonded fixed partial denture (RBFDP) was tried in the mouth (Fig. 05) and the necessary occlusal corrections were made. The metal portion of the intaglio surface was sand blasted before cementation. The cementation was carried out using self cure resin cement. The prepared enamel surfaces and gingival seats were etched with 37% phosphoric acid etchant gel for 20 seconds. Later dentin primer was applied. A mix of two-paste resin cement was made and applied on the fitted surface of the prosthesis, and it was finally cemented into position⁴.

The final esthetic result obtained was as follows (Fig. 06).

Fig. 06: The prosthesis cemented with a good esthetic result and no display of metal on the buccal side.

Discussion

This design may be slightly more invasive than more traditional methods for preparing the abutments for Resin-bonded fixed partial dentures (RBFDPs). However it remains less invasive and less costly compared with the complete coverage or partial coverage conventional Fixed Partial Dentures (FPDs)⁵. Impression procedures do not require gingival retraction and hence are much simpler. Time for preparation and for provisional restoration is also greatly reduced. However, the cementation procedure is time-consuming and requires strict adherence to the manufacturer's instructions to ensure long-term success.

This modified design for the posterior Resin-bonded fixed partial denture (RBFDP) is best suited for those clinical situations where there is no more than one missing tooth, and when the abutments are either intact or have only small proximal carious lesions or restoration. A formal long term clinical trial is needed to test the long-term performance of this modified design⁶.

Summary

This method involves some modifications in the preparation and casting design. It also requires slightly more time and attention at the cementation procedure.

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Bilateral Absence of Frontal Sinus and Unilateral Mandibular Hypoplasia

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Abstract

Absence of frontal sinus is usually associated with various syndromes such as craniosynostosis, osteodysplasia, down syndrome etc. Geographically, absence of frontal sinus is seen usually in areas with cold climate. This paper reports a case of 18-year old Indian woman suffering from bilateral absence of frontal sinuses which was non-syndromic in conjunction with unilateral mandibular hypoplasia. The paper also highlights the clinical significance of frontal sinus which was non-syndromic absence and its rarity in warm climate such as in South East Asian regions and the treatment options of unilateral mandibular hypoplasia.

Keywords: Frontal sinus, Hypoplasia, Non-syndromic.

Introduction

Soft and bone tissue facial asymmetry is seen in patients with and without facial cosmetic alterations. The etiology is believed to be related to congenital, developmental, or acquired factors.

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In some cases, asymmetry may be secondary to condylar hyperplasia or hypoplasia, ankylosis, or hemifacial microsomia. The importance of the head of the condyle as the main growth centre of the mandible was first fully realized by Wilson Charles (1925). Its significance in producing facial deformity when there is interference with this growth centre due to trauma or infection has been fully described by Rushton (1944) and Greer Walker (1957).

The growth of the skull, maxilla, and mandible are closely related. If growth is decompensated in one of these areas, the asymmetric growth and development of part of the craniofacial skeleton may result in a chin deviated from the mandibular midline. Patients with deviated chins usually present asymmetries in other portions of the facial skeleton. Genetic and trauma-related asymmetries may involve muscles, produce excessive unilateral growth, or adversely affect mandible development.

Facial asymmetry is considered to be present even in normal craniofacial complexes, and a cant of 0-3 mm may be deemed normal in healthy unaffected patients. The structures on the lower third of the face are usually more asymmetric than those in the middle third. According to the literature, the left side of the face is usually more affected due to genetic predisposition.

Frontal sinuses are pneumatic cavities that become radiologically evident at the age of five or six years and develop fully by the age of 20 years. Studies have suggested that the frontal sinuses are slightly bigger in males than in females, and the presence of a metopic suture is associated with the absence of the frontal sinuses. Paranasal sinuses are prone to a great diversity of anomalies.

The underdevelopment or aplasia of the paranasal sinuses is a rare phenomenon that refers mainly to the frontal (12%) and secondarily to the maxillary sinuses (5–6%). This occurs more frequently in syndromes of craniosynostosis, osteodysplasia (Melnick-Needles), as well as in cases of Down's syndrome (hypoplasia of the frontal sinus). It is important for surgeons to be aware of variations that may predispose patients to increased risk of intra operative complications and help avoid possible complications and improve success of management strategies.

Bilateral absence of frontal sinus is rare. The aim of this article is to report a case of unilateral mandibular hypoplasia with bilateral absence of frontal sinus which was non syndromic.

Case Report

An 18-year-old Indian woman reported to the department of Oral Medicine and Radiology, Dental College, MM University, India with a complaint of a deviated chin. Patient's history revealed that the patient first noticed facial asymmetry 10 years back, which has gradually increased with time. Since then, the patient also complained of pain in the region of the ear occasionally, on the same side. The pain was dull, intermittent in nature, radiated towards the region of head and eye and relived upon itself. On examination, there was no intra oral finding except class III malocclusion and the presence of facial asymmetry with chin deviated towards the right side (Figure 01).

Figure 01: Presence of facial asymmetry with chin deviated towards the right side.

On radiographic examinations, Panoramic radiograph revealed hypoplasia of mandibular body and ramus including mandible condyle on right side. There was also presence of prominent antegonial notch on right side (Figure 02).

Figure 02: Panoramic radiograph revealed hypoplasia of mandibular body and ramus including mandible condyle on right side with prominent antegonial notch.

Water's view revealed that the patient had mandibular asymmetry and presence of bilateral absence of frontal sinus (Figure 03).

Figure 03: Water's view revealed the patient had mandibular asymmetry and presence of bilateral absence of frontal sinus.

CT scan revealed mandibular hypoplasia on right side with hypoplasia of mandible condyle and resultant retrognathism (Figure 04). Mild flattening of right condyloid fossa and articular eminence was also present. Bilateral frontal sinuses were absent (Figure 05).

Figure 04: CT scan revealed mandibular hypoplasia on right side with hypoplasia of mandible condyle and resultant retrognathism.

Figure 05: Mild flattening of right condyloid fossa and articular eminence was also present. Bilateral frontal sinuses were absent.

Discussion

A hypoplastic mandible can occur as an isolated entity or as part of the following first arch syndromes: (Pierre Robin anomaly, Treacher Collins, cri du chat, trisomies, and Goldenhar's). In our case, hypoplastic mandible was present with bilateral absence of frontal sinuses.

Unlike teeth with periodontal-related lesions, teeth with endodontic-related lesions mainly feature extensive restorations. In contrast to teeth with endodontal lesions, periodontal lesions are often visible in combination with local factors (plaque/calculus). Whereas periodontal-related lesions which generally involve increased exploratory depth, endodontal related lesions as in the case mentioned; during probing, at one particular aspect of the tooth, the probe 'disappears' into a deep, narrow, fistula-like defect.

Three systemic factors, i.e. the craniofacial configuration, the thickness of frontal bone and growth hormone levels influence frontal sinus morphology. According to Koertvelyessey, who studied the frontal sinus of 153 Eskimo crania, the degree of pneumatization correlates positively with the degree of environmental coldness in which the population lives.

Frontal sinus patterns have a potential to be used as aids for personal identification, age estimation, and sexual dimorphism. They have been found to have individual morphological variations. Thus, the reliability of comparing ante- and post-mortem radiographs of the frontal sinus for identification is well founded.

Owing to anatomic variability of the frontal sinuses, the neurosurgical approach to the orbit by the anterior cranial fossa in a patient with an inflammatory nasal pathology may jeopardize the sterility of surgical field.⁶ In patients with large pneumatization, the possible inadvertent entry into the frontal sinus may occur during a peritoneal craniotomy for the microtomy for the microsurgical clipping of aneurysms. This situation may require a frontal sinus cranialization or an osteoplastic frontal sinus operation with fat obliteration.

Therefore, the preoperative recognition of the frontal sinuses is a prerequisite for any successful surgical procedure because of individual anatomic variations. Patients with class III malocclusion combined with facial asymmetry in which the mandibular midline does not match the chin midline require mandibular bilateral sagittal osteotomy. However, the patient's perceptions over their condition must be taken into account as suggested in our case.

Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to present a case of unilateral mandibular hypoplasia which was idiopathic in nature in conjunction with absence of bilateral frontal sinuses. Absence of frontal sinuses shows racial differences. Environmental factors, i.e a warm climate, might also be related to the low frequency of frontal sinus aplasia. Lower frequency might be appropriate as an identification procedure. On the other hand, neurosurgeons should be prepared for the inadvertent entry during the surgical interventions as mentioned earlier.

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Split Cast Metal Post and Core

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Abstract

This case report presents restoration of an endodontically treated carious broken mandibular first molar with divergent roots, restored with split-cast post and core fabricated by direct technique. Endodontic treatment of a mutilated tooth may prove unfruitful if it is not well restored to bear the forces of occlusion. So the options of prosthetic reconstruction should be well considered before attempting endodontic treatment on badly broken teeth. In such cases post is the choice of restoration as it serves to retain core. Badly broken molar was preserved by using multiple posts in the divergent canals. Non parallel accessory posts was used as it increased the retentive surface area of the cast post and core, minimized the chance of root perforation during tooth preparation and also redistribute the forces of occlusion. An ideal post system should have the ability to distribute the functional stresses evenly along the root surface and produce minimal stress during placement and cementation. The clinician should select the right type of post and core system considering the biological, mechanical and esthetic needs for each individual tooth.

Keywords: Custom made post and core, Direct technique, Non parallel post, Split cast post and core.

Introduction

Posterior teeth lie in the closer proximity of transverse horizontal axis. An endodontically treated posterior tooth should be provided with proper cuspal coverage to prevent its fracture from occlusal forces and at the same time it should be relieved of potentially damaging lateral forces during excursive movements. Posterior teeth often have curved roots and the predominant canal shape is ovoid.

As the commercially available pre-fabricated posts commonly have round cross section and parallel walls, such posts are unlikely to adapt well with the canal walls along their entire interface, with luting cement occupying greater canal space. For these teeth, retention is better achieved by two or more relatively short posts in the divergent canals¹.

Choice between a custom designed post and a prefabricated post should be made by analyzing the canal configuration². Conservative option is to select the post that closely conforms to the canal shape and size because less dentin removal is required and thus enhancing fracture resistance of the tooth as well as retention of the post^{3,4}. It has been suggested that if a canal requires extensive preparation a well adapted cast post and core restoration will be more retentive than a prefabricated post that does not match the canal shape⁵. The cast post and core is custom fitted to the prepared root canal space and designed to resist torsional forces.

Considering the amount of tooth material removal for crown preparation and the amount of dentin removal in access cavity and canal preparation, a passively fitting post- core seems to be the only radiculo-coronal stabilizer for the weakened tooth. In maxillary molars, palatal canal serves as primary site in for hosting post, while mesio-buccal and disto-buccal serve as secondary canals. While in mandibular molar, distal is the primary canal and mesio-buccal and mesio-lingual act as secondary canals.

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Case report

A twenty five year old female patient was referred to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics with chief complaint of pain in the lower right posterior region since five days. A history of dull pain for last two years was associated with the same tooth. The pain intensified during any thermal stimulus and upon mastication. Patient's medical history was non-contributory. On clinical examination, tooth number 46 was found to have deep carious lesion with undermined lingual wall. The tooth was tender to palpation and percussion. Heat test using gutta percha stick revealed a lingering pain after the removal of stimulus. Radiographic examination revealed occlusal radiolucency involving pulp space and widening of the periodontal ligament space (Fig.1a). The diagnosis of acute irreversible pulpitis with acute apical periodontitis was made. With patient's consent endodontic treatment was started. Working length was established radiographically (Fig.1b) and the canals were obturated with gutta percha (Fig.1c).

After the proper endodontic treatment challenge was to restore the tooth to proper function with a good coronal restoration. As the lingual wall of the crown was grossly undermined treatment option was restoration of the tooth with a custom made cast post and core followed by full crown. As the roots were divergent, a split cast metal post and core (non-parallel) was planned.

Coronal preparation was performed for PFM crown and for fabrication of posts 7 mm of gutta percha was removed from the coronal part of distal canal and 4 mm from the mesio-buccal canal with the help of piezo reamer (Fig.1i). Auto-polymerizing acrylic resin was used to prepare the post pattern for distal canal. Resin was mixed and rolled into thin cylinder. This was then introduced into the pre-lubricated distal canal and pushed to place by dipping in the monomer. Bead brush technique was used to add resin until the post snugly fitted the canal. Resin was not allowed to harden completely within the canal. It was loosened and resealed several times while still in rubbery stage. Once the resin got polymerized, it was removed and the undercuts were identified and trimmed away carefully with the help of scalpel. The post was then trimmed to give it a continuous tapering shape from occlusal to apical direction. Using the same procedure post pattern was also prepared for mesio-buccal canal.

Now the core was prepared attached to post pattern of mesio-buccal canal. Autopolymerizing acrylic resin was mixed and placed in the pulp chamber.

Petroleum jelly was applied over the earlier prepared post pattern of the distal canal and introduced into the distal canal penetrating through the unpolymerized resin of the core material. Petroleum jelly acted as separating media preventing the polymerization of the distal post with the polymerizing core resin. Distal post pattern was repeatedly removed and resealed into the canal to check for its withdrawal from the core material. Once the core material polymerized completely it was removed. Split cast post and core pattern was so prepared, which consisted of a distal post and a mesio-buccal post which had the core attached to it. The core had a pathway in it through which the distal post could be inserted (Fig.1e & f).

The resin patterns for both the canals were separately sprued, invested and casted with Type III cast gold alloy (Fig.1g). After finishing the castings adjustments were first made for the distal post so that it could pass easily through the pathway in the core attached to the mesio-buccal post (Fig.1h). Then both the posts were adjusted to fit properly inside the canals one by one. Final adjustment was done by first placing the mesio-buccal post and core in mesial root and then placing the distal post through it (Fig.1j). Cementation was done using resin cement. The mesio-buccal post and core was luted first followed by distal post (Fig.1d). Final restoration was done with PFM crown (Fig.1k).

Figure. 1

Discussion

An endodontically treated and restored tooth loses much of its natural tooth structure due to caries decalcification, access cavity preparation and crown preparation. It is this loss of structural integrity rather than the changes in dentin that lead to a higher occurrence of fractures in endodontically treated teeth compared with "vital" teeth⁶.

Access preparations result in increased cuspal deflection during function⁷ and increase the possibility of cuspal fracture and micro leakage at the margins of restorations. Randow and Glantz⁸ reported that teeth have a protective feedback mechanism that is lost when the pulp is removed which may also contribute to tooth fracture.

Consequently such teeth demand a restoration that will not only conserve remaining tooth structure but also provide strength and support to the remaining part. Intra-radicular restorations have been proved to restore such weakened teeth to their natural functions. The choice of these restorations can be made between two systems - conventional custom cast post and core and commercially available prefabricated post systems⁹.

Custom cast posts and cores are generally recommended for posterior as well as anterior teeth with grossly decayed crown structure. The cast post and core is custom fitted to the prepared root canal space and designed to resist torsional forces. According to Morgano¹⁰ and Heydeche¹¹ custom fabricated cast post and cores are still the established technique or gold standard for restoring extensively damaged teeth.

Smith² and Ash¹² stated that canal configuration aids in making a choice between a custom designed post and a prefabricated post. The selected post should closely conform to the canal shape and size to make restoration more conservative as this requires less dentin removal, enhances fracture resistance of the tooth and also enhances retention of the post and core system. The primary reason for using a post is to retain the core that substitutes the missing coronal tooth structure. Therefore the post head design is an important factor. The post head should provide adequate retention and resistance to displacement of the core material. Studies have reported that prefabricated metal posts with direct core made of glass ionomer, composite or amalgam are less reliable than a one piece cast post and core because of the interface between the post and the core.

The recommendations for the split cast metal post and core design discussed here are for the teeth having divergent roots with canals not allowing the same path of insertion for the posts. In this case report there is a different path of insertion for both the posts.

Conclusions

Custom cast post and core are recommended for non circular root canals and when coronal tooth structure loss is moderate to severe. Split cast metal post and core design can be used for additional retention in teeth having divergent roots and in which canals do not allow same path of insertion for the posts.

Simplified design and ease of fabrication are the major advantages of this case report. The technique can be accomplished in any dental clinic without using any complicated equipment.

Clinical Significance

The clinician should select the right type of post and core system considering the biological, mechanical and esthetic needs for each individual tooth. An ideal post system should have the ability to distribute the functional stresses evenly along the root surface, should be esthetically compatible with the definitive restoration and surrounding tissue and produce minimal stress during placement and cementation.

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